

A Study of Two Fractional Integral Problems Based on Jumarie Type of Riemann-Liouville Fractional Calculus

Chii-Huei Yu

School of Mathematics and Statistics, Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982262>

Published Date: 23-October-2024

Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional calculus, we find the exact solutions of two fractional integrals. Integration by parts for fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions play important roles in this article. In fact, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus, fractional integrals, integration by parts for fractional calculus, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus studies the so-called fractional integral and derivative of real or complex order and their applications. It originated in 1695, in a letter written by L'Hospital to Leibniz, some problems are proposed, such as "what does fractional derivative mean?" or "what is the 1/2 derivative of a function?" In the 18th and 19th centuries, many outstanding scientists focused their attention on this problem. For example, Euler, Laplace, Fourier, Abel, Liouville, Grünwald, Letnikov, Riemann, Laurent, or Heaviside. In the past few decades, fractional calculus has been applied to many fields, such as mechanics, economics, viscoelasticity, biology, control theory, and electrical engineering [1-15].

However, the definition of fractional derivative is not unique. Common definitions include Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative, Caputo fractional derivative, Grünwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative [16-20]. Since Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative helps to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function, it is easier to use this definition to connect fractional calculus with classical calculus.

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus, we obtain the exact solutions of the following two α -fractional integrals:

$$({}_{-\infty}I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes p} \otimes E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \right],$$

and

$$\left({}_{[\Gamma(\alpha+1)]\frac{1}{\alpha}}I_t^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes(q-1)} \otimes [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)]^{\otimes p} \right],$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $(-1)^\alpha$ exists and p, q are positive integers. Integration by parts for fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions play important roles in this paper. In fact, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Firstly, we introduce the fractional derivative used in this paper and its properties.

Definition 2.1 ([21]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt. \quad (1)$$

And the Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville α -fractional integral is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}I_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma(\)$ is the gamma function.

Proposition 2.2 ([22]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x-x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (4)$$

Next, we introduce the definition of fractional analytic function.

Definition 2.3 ([23]): If x, x_0 , and a_k are real numbers for all k , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{k\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced below.

Definition 2.4 ([24]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. If $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (6)$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Definition 2.5 ([25]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (9)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (10)$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (11)$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (12)$$

Definition 2.6 ([26]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ be two α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \dots \otimes_\alpha f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$. On the other hand, if $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1$, then $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the $\otimes_\alpha$ reciprocal of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, and is denoted by $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha -1}$.

Definition 2.7 ([27]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real variable. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (13)$$

And the α -fractional logarithmic function $Ln_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is the inverse function of $E_\alpha(x^\alpha)$.

Theorem 2.8 (integration by parts for fractional calculus) ([28]): Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, a, b are real numbers, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are α -fractional analytic functions, then

$$\left({}_a I_b^\alpha \right) \left[f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \left({}_a D_x^\alpha \right) [g_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \right] = \left[f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \right]_{x=a}^{x=b} - \left({}_a I_b^\alpha \right) \left[g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \left({}_a D_x^\alpha \right) [f_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \right]. \quad (14)$$

Notation 2.9: If r is any real number, p is any positive integer. Define $(r)_p = r(r-1) \dots (r-p+1)$, and $(r)_0 = 1$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we find the exact solutions of two fractional integrals.

Theorem 3.1: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $(-1)^\alpha$ exists and p, q are positive integers, then the α -fractional integral

$$\left({}_{-\infty} I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \right] = E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \frac{(p)_k}{q^{k+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (p-k)}. \quad (15)$$

Proof : By integration by parts for fractional calculus,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left({}_{-\infty} I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \right] \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{q} E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \right]_{x=-\infty}^{x=x} - \left({}_{-\infty} I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\frac{1}{q} E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \left({}_{-\infty} D_x^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) - \frac{p}{q} \left({}_{-\infty} I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (p-1)} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \right] \\ &= \dots \\ &= E_\alpha(qx^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \frac{(p)_k}{q^{k+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (p-k)}. \end{aligned} \quad \text{q.e.d.}$$

Theorem 3.2: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $(-1)^\alpha$ exists and p, q are positive integers, then the α -fractional integral

$$\left(\left[\Gamma(\alpha+1) \right]_{\frac{1}{\alpha}} I_t^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes(q-1)} \otimes_\alpha [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)]^{\otimes p} \right] = \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha q} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \frac{(p)_k}{q^{k+1}} (Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha (p-k)}. \quad (16)$$

Proof: In Theorem 3.1, let $Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha$, then $(Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha p} = \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p}$ and

$$\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha q} = E_\alpha(q Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)) = E_\alpha(q x^\alpha). \quad (17)$$

And

$$\left(\left[\Gamma(\alpha+1) \right]_{\frac{1}{\alpha}} D_t^\alpha \right) [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)] = (-\infty D_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right] = 1. \quad (18)$$

Thus, by Theorem 3.1

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left[\Gamma(\alpha+1) \right]_{\frac{1}{\alpha}} I_t^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes(q-1)} \otimes [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)]^{\otimes p} \right] \\ &= \left(\left[\Gamma(\alpha+1) \right]_{\frac{1}{\alpha}} I_t^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes q} \otimes [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)]^{\otimes p} \otimes_\alpha \left(\left[\Gamma(\alpha+1) \right]_{\frac{1}{\alpha}} D_t^\alpha \right) [Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha)] \right] \\ &= (-\infty I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha(q x^\alpha) \right] \\ &= E_\alpha(q x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \frac{(p)_k}{q^{k+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (p-k)} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} t^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha q} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^p (-1)^k \frac{(p)_k}{q^{k+1}} (Ln_\alpha(t^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha (p-k)}. \end{aligned} \quad \text{q.e.d.}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus, we find the exact solutions of two fractional integrals. Integration by parts for fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions play important roles in this article. In fact, the major results we obtained are natural generalizations of the results in classical calculus. In the future, we will continue to use our methods to study the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. L. Bagley and P. J. Torvik, A theoretical basis for the application of fractional calculus to viscoelasticity, Journal of Rheology, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 201-210, 1983.
- [2] R. Almeida, N. R. Bastos, and M. T. T. Monteiro, Modeling some real phenomena by fractional differential equations, Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences, vol. 39, no. 16, pp. 4846-4855, 2016.
- [3] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering, Advanced Engineering Technology and Application, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41-45, 2016.
- [4] R. Magin, Fractional calculus in bioengineering, part 1, Critical Reviews in Biomedical Engineering, vol. 32, no.1, pp.1-104, 2004.
- [5] E. Soczkiewicz, Application of fractional calculus in the theory of viscoelasticity, Molecular and Quantum Acoustics vol.23, pp. 397-404, 2002.
- [6] V. E. Tarasov, Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus, Mathematics, vol. 8, no. 5, 660, 2020.
- [7] J. T. Machado, Fractional Calculus: Application in Modeling and Control, Springer New York, 2013.

- [8] F. Mainardi, Fractional calculus: some basic problems in continuum and statistical mechanics, *Fractals and Fractional Calculus in Continuum Mechanics*, pp. 291-348, Springer, Wien, Germany, 1997.
- [9] H. A. Fallahgoul, S. M. Focardi and F. J. Fabozzi, *Fractional calculus and fractional processes with applications to financial economics, theory and application*, Elsevier Science and Technology, 2016.
- [10] M. F. Silva, J. A. T. Machado, and I. S. Jesus, Modelling and simulation of walking robots with 3 dof legs, in *Proceedings of the 25th IASTED International Conference on Modelling, Identification and Control (MIC '06)*, pp. 271-276, Lanzarote, Spain, 2006.
- [11] M. Teodor, Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, *Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [12] C. -H. Yu, A study on fractional RLC circuit, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 3422-3425, 2020.
- [13] C. -H. Yu, A new insight into fractional logistic equation, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp.13-17, 2021.
- [14] R. Hilfer (Ed.), *Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics*, WSPC, Singapore, 2000.
- [15] F. Duarte and J. A. T. Machado, Chaotic phenomena and fractional-order dynamics in the trajectory control of redundant manipulators, *Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 29, no. 1-4, pp. 315-342, 2002.
- [16] I. Podlubny, *Fractional Differential Equations*, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.
- [17] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, *The Fractional Calculus*, Academic Press, Inc., 1974.
- [18] K. S. Miller and B. Ross, *An introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations*, A Wiley-Interscience Publication, John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA, 1993.
- [19] S. Das, *Functional Fractional Calculus for System Identification and Control*, 2nd ed., Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2011.
- [20] K. Diethelm, *The Analysis of Fractional Differential Equations*, Springer-Verlag, 2010. [18]. C. -H. Yu, Study of fractional analytic functions and local fractional calculus, *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 39-46, 2021.
- [21] C. -H. Yu, Study on some properties of fractional analytic function, *International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Technology*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 31-35, 2022.
- [22] C. -H. Yu, A Study of some fractional differential problems, *International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 52-58, 2022.
- [23] C. -H. Yu, Exact solution of linear system of fractional differential equations with constant coefficients, *International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Technology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1-7, 2022.
- [24] C. -H. Yu, Application of differentiation under fractional integral sign, *International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 40-46, 2022.
- [25] C. -H. Yu, Fractional differential problem of some fractional trigonometric functions, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 48-53, 2022.
- [26] C. -H. Yu, Infinite series expressions for the values of some fractional analytic functions, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 80-85, 2023.
- [27] C. -H. Yu, Study of two fractional integrals, *International Journal of Novel Research in Physics Chemistry & Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1-6, 2023.
- [28] C. -H. Yu, Application of integration by parts for fractional calculus in solving two types of fractional definite integrals, *International Journal of Novel Research in Electrical and Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 79-84, 2023.